

Capacity of a Neural PDE

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Abstract

In this review-note we are interested in determining the information bearing properties and abilities of the Hodgkin Huxley equation.

Introduction and Preliminaries

Ikeda and Manton [1] provide the capacity formula for a single spiking neuron channel. Here we are interested in a tract of N axons [2]. We start with the $N = 1$ case:

$$C \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = G^{ax} \cos^2 \theta \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial z^2} - G^{my} V + I^{inj, ion} \quad (1)$$

and write its capacity as:

$$Cap = \max I(V(0, [0, T]); V(L, [0, T])). \quad (2)$$

Using $\phi_i(0, T)$ as a C.O.N. set of basis functions [3] we write $V(0, [0, T])$ as

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} v_{0i} \phi_i(0, T). \quad (3)$$

Therefore $V(0, [0, T]) \equiv \{v_{0i}\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$, an equivalence in representation. Similarly, $V(L, [0, T]) \equiv \{v_{Li}\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$. Therefore, if

$$\alpha_i = f_{v_{0i}(v_{0i})}^{max} subj.to P \quad (4)$$

where P is the power constraint, then

$$Cap_i = \alpha_i I(\{v_{0i}\}_{i=1}^{\infty}; \{v_{Li}\}_{i=1}^{\infty}). \quad (5)$$

Now, the condition for complete orthonormality is

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi_i(0, T) \cdot \phi_j(0, T) dt = \begin{cases} 0, & i \neq j \\ 1, & i = j \end{cases}$$

and

$$V(0, [0, T]) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} v_{0i} \phi_i(0, T). \quad (6)$$

Project both sides of Equation (6) onto the CON set, to get

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi_j(0, T) V(0, [0, T]) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi_j(0, T) \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} v_{0i} \phi_i(0, T)$$

Switching the order of the summation and integration, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} v_{0i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi_i \phi_j dt \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} v_{0i} \begin{cases} 0, & i \neq j \\ 1, & i = j \end{cases} \\ &= v_{0j} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$v_{0j} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi_j(0, T) \cdot V(0, [0, T]) dt \quad (7)$$

and

$$v_{Lj} = \langle \phi_j(0, T), V(L, [0, T]) \rangle. \quad (8)$$

Determining $H(v_{0j})$

Assume v_{0j} belong to a discrete set. This is possible if there are only a few stimulus waveforms. In this scenario, let $v_{0j} \in [v_{0j}^1, v_{0j}^2, \dots, v_{0j}^k]$. Then,

$$H(v_{0j}) = - \sum_{i=1}^k p_i \log p_i \quad (9)$$

where $p_i = Pr(v_{0j} = v_{0j}^i)$. Assuming a uniform prior, we have $p_i = \frac{1}{k}$. Call this, assumption (**). This implies,

$$H(v_{0j}) = - \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{k} \log\left(\frac{1}{k}\right), \quad (10)$$

where k is the total number of possible stimuli.

Determining $H(v_{0j}|v_{Lj})$

By definition,

$$H(v_{0j}|v_{Lj}) = -\mathbb{E}_{v_{Lj}} \left[\sum_{i=1}^k Pr(v_{0j}^i | v_{Lj}) \cdot \log(Pr(v_{0j}^i | v_{Lj})) \right] \quad (11)$$

Determining $Pr(v_{0j}^i|v_{Lj})$

As per Bayes' formula [4],

$$Pr(v_{0j}^i|v_{Lj}) = \frac{Pr(v_{Lj}|v_{0j}^i) \cdot Pr(v_{0j}^i)}{Pr(v_{Lj})}. \quad (12)$$

Using the uniform prior, this yields

$$Pr(v_{0j}^i|v_{Lj}) = \frac{Pr(v_{Lj}|v_{0j}^i)}{k \cdot Pr(v_{Lj})}. \quad (13)$$

Further suppose that v_{Lj} also belong to a discrete set of size F . Then, $Pr(v_{Lj}|v_{0j}^i)$ which stands for $Pr(v_{Lj} = v_{Lj}^m|v_{0j}^i)$, can be equated with $\beta_{L|0}(m|i)$ which is the transition matrix of the 'channel.'

Next, we use the total probability theorem [5] to write,

$$Pr(v_{Lj} = v_{Lj}^m) = \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{L|0}(m|i) \cdot Pr(i) \quad (14)$$

Now,

$$Pr(v_{0j}^i|v_{Lj}^m) = \frac{Pr(v_{Lj}|v_{0j}^i)}{k \cdot Pr(v_{Lj}^m)} = \frac{\beta_{L|0}(m|i)}{\sum_{n=1}^k \beta_{L|0}(m|n)} \quad (15)$$

This allows us to determine $H(v_{0j}|v_{Lj})$. Thus, we in essence have $I(v_{0i}; v_{Li})$.

Next Steps and Conclusion

Our next step is to relax assumption (**), in order to get the general mutual information. Then we may maximize it over choices of $\{p_i\}$ subject to power or cost constraints. Numerical simulations can also be invoked and might be useful, especially for $N > 1$.

References

- [1] Shiro Ikeda and Jonathan H Manton. Capacity of a single spiking neuron channel. *Neural Computation*, 21(6):1714–1748, 2009.
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